

THE INFLUENCE OF PROFESSIONAL SKEPTICISM AND PROFESSIONAL ETHICS TO THE ACCURACY PUBLISH OF AUDITOR OPINION (PAF CASE STUDY IN BANDUNG)

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Abstract

The study was designed to see if there is a correlation between professional ethics and accuracy when giving an audit opinion. The more rules put in place for the PAF, the more problems there tend to be. Quantitative research uses measurements to study things. The people in this study are people who work as auditors at a Public Accounting Firm in Bandung, Indonesia. They were all registered with the Financial Services Authority in 2022. The survey was conducted using a questionnaire that uses the cluster sampling technique. This means that different people were asked other questions in different places. The study found that multiple linear regression analysis is a reliable way to analyze data. This method is used to find out what factors are important in predicting a result. The program used to analyze the data is called SPSS. It is a beneficial program that can help us understand the data better. The study found that professional skepticism about auditing affects how accurately auditors can give their opinions. The auditor's professional ethics can affect an auditor's opinion accuracy.

Keywords: Accuracy Publish of Auditor Opinion, Professional Skepticism, Professional Ethics, Public Accounting Firm.

INTRODUCTION

A Public Accounting Firm (KAP) needs financial statement audit services before policymakers make decisions. Financial reports that have been audited by a Public Accounting Firm (PAF) are one of the benchmarks for the fairness of a company's financial statements. Audited financial statements are more reliable than unaudited or unaudited financial statements (Kiswanti & Hanah, 2021). The public accounting profession is a profession that is trusted by the public. Public confidence in the quality of services provided by auditors will be higher if the industry applies high-quality standards to the implementation of professional work by industry members. It is from this public accounting profession that one expects an independent assessment of the information provided by the company's management in its financial statements. The public accounting profession is expected to improve its performance by delivering audit products in the form of reliable opinions to those in need (L. Dewi & Asmaranti, 2015).

Public Accounting Firms have clearer responsibilities and more professional requirements that public accounting firms must meet than other organizations because of their greater commitment to users of audit reports. Public Accounting Firms have the legal right to carry out financial statements based on applicable regulations (Jaya, 2013). In recent years various

events have presented challenges for public accountants. An audit phenomenon published is that the audit quality of Public Accounting Firms in Indonesia is still inadequate because many small-scale Public Accounting Firms do not adequately apply Quality Control Standards (QCS). The results of the 2018 Financial Professional Development Center (FPDC) periodic inspection of the Big 10 PAFs and non-Big 10 PAFs. The Big 10 PAF is one of the best and largest PAFs that are active and serve large companies in Indonesia. The big 10 PAFs consist of Deloitte (PAF Osman Bing Satrio), PwC (PricewaterhouseCoopers) (PAF Haryanto Sahari), Ernst & Young (PAF Purwantono, Sarwoko, Sandjaja), KPMG (PAF Sidharta, Sidharta, Widjaja), RSM (McGladrey & Pullen), Grant Thornton, CBIZ (Mayer Hoffman McCann), BDO (USA), Crowe Horwath, and BKD there are many findings of non-compliance with audit standards. Here is a graph:

Figure 1: Findings Based on PAF Size in 2018

Based on figure 1, for non-Big 10 PAFs, there were 692 findings with a percentage of 92%; for Big 10 PAF, there were 60 findings with a ratio of 8%. The PAFs that do the most non-compliance with auditing standards are Non-Big 10 PAF.

Figure 2: Distribution of Non-Big 10 PAF Findings

Based on figure 2, the examination conducted on 52 non-Big 10 PAF public accountants found 464 findings of non-compliance, with the most dominating finding which means that public accountants have not fully complied with professional standards. Non-compliance with the

implementation of the Quality Control System (QCS), there are as many as 145 findings, and in the Design of QCS, there are as many as 43 findings, which means that public accountants still need to comply with and implement QCS fully. Article 27 of Law Number 5 of the Year 2011 concerning Public Accountants requires PAF to have and operate a quality control system following the applicable FPDC control standards of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Finance. The PAF Quality Control System must refer to the QCS set by IAPI and become effective January 1, 2013. Public confidence in the public accounting profession has decreased because many companies went bankrupt after receiving unqualified financial statements. As happened in the following phenomena that received an unqualified opinion, including the following:

Table 1: Problematic PAF data

Name of Public Accounting Firm	Violations Committed
PT Asuransi Jiwasraya, PT Asabrin and PAF Soejatna, Mulyana, and Partners.	Giving opinions not following the code of ethics or auditing standards on the financial statements.
PT Sunprima Nusantara Pembiayaan (SNP), Akuntan Publik (AP) Marlinna, and Merliyana Syamsul, and Public Accounting Firm (PAF) Satrio, Bing, Eny and Partners	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of professional skepticism of public accountants and ethical standards in providing audit services 2) Both APs provide opinions that do not reflect the actual condition of the company 3) 3. As a result of the discrepancy in the opinion of the financial statements, it causes losses to the financial services industry and the public.

Table 1 the case of PT Asuransi Jiwasraya and PT Asabri involved a public accounting firm (PAF) that was found to have provided opinions that were not following the code of ethics or standards. The PAF statement says that the financial statements of PT Asuransi Jiwasraya (Persero) and its subsidiaries as of December 31, 2016, are unqualified. Jiwasraya's net income increased by 37% in 2016. This was shown in their signed audited financial statements from PwC. The financial statements still need to be published, but they are becoming more consolidated. This means that the different financial reports are combined into one document. According to the Jiwasraya website, Jiwasraya had a net profit of 2.1 trillion in 2016 and 328 billion in 2017. This is an unqualified opinion, and the numbers have been audited by PwC. There are some things that happen in the world that skeptics might study, and others that happen when an accountant is independent. The Ministry of Finance has taken action against three public accountants, which means they have been blocked from doing their jobs.

The three public accountants who were sanctioned were Public Accountant Marlinna, Public Accountant Merliyana Syamsul, and Public Accounting Firm Satrio, Bing, Eny and Partners. They were not allowed to provide opinions that matched the actual conditions in SNP Finance's

annual audited financial statements. This doesn't look like the kind of thing that is allowed in the park. We use Public Accounting and PAF services so that we can communicate more easily with each other. The auditor did something wrong by helping to tamper with data about the services he was providing. The finance minister of Scotland, Sri Mulani, believes that there is a lack of skepticism in the professionalism of public accountants and that this is leading to problems with the quality of audit services.

There is an update to the Regulation of the Minister of Finance, namely Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 154/PMK.01/2017 which needs to be refined and replaced with a new Regulation of the Minister of Finance to improve the quality of the Public Accountant profession to increase public trust (Indonesia, 2017). The new regulation was changed to Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 186/PMK.01/2021 concerning the Guidance and Supervision of the Public Accountant Profession. However, based on the 2019 FPDC examination conducted on 52 non-Big 10 PAF public accountants, 464 findings of non-compliance with standards were the most dominating, which means that public accountants still need to comply with professional standards fully (Indonesia, 2021). The emergence of these findings makes the public's lack of trust in the public accounting profession reasonable.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Relationship of Professional Skepticism to Auditor Opinion

Gusti and Ali, it was found that there is a significant relationship between the auditor's professional skepticism and the accuracy of giving the auditor's opinion of a public accountant (Gusti & Ali, 2008). The results of this study support the research conducted by Ida Suraida who found that there is a large influence between the auditor's professional skepticism on the accuracy of giving an auditor's opinion by a public accountant (Suraida, 2005).

Research conducted by Adnyani, Atmadja, & Herawati concerning the effect of professional skepticism on giving opinions to auditors in providing more and more significant information results than auditors who have a low level of professional skepticism, and this results in auditors having skepticism High professionals will be more able to detect fraud because of the information they have (Adnyani et al., 2014). Research conducted by Royae, Nezhad, & Azinfar concluded that professional skepticism has a positive effect on giving an auditor's opinion (Royae et al., 2013). Likewise, Mardijuwono & Subianto explained in his research that professional skepticism has a positive impact on an auditor's ability to give an opinion (Mardijuwono & Subianto, 2018). This was confirmed by Dewi & Asmaranti in her research which found that an auditor who has professional skepticism is able to provide the maximum and objective opinion on his reporting (L. Dewi & Asmaranti, 2015).

Hypothesis 1: Professional Skepticism has a positive effect on Auditor Opinion

Relationship of Professional Ethics to Auditor Opinion

Cognitive dissonance theory can explain that the emergence of inconsistencies in the auditor to follow or not follow some of the codes of ethics, as well as differences in individual

perceptions regarding ethical or unethical matters, can lead to harmony in professional ethics, he will be able to carry out his audit properly according to what is required in the professional code of ethics (Sila et al., 2016). The results of Kamil & Fathonah research show empirically that ethical factors have a positive effect on the accuracy of giving opinions (Kamil & Fathonah, 2020). The research results of Rahmina & Agoes are also a reference for writers who state that ethics also influences the accuracy of giving opinions by auditors (Rahmina & Agoes, 2014). Likewise, Suryanto prove that there is a positive influence of professional ethics on the accuracy of giving opinions (Suryanto, 2015).

Hypothesis 2: Professional Ethics has a positive effect on Auditor Opinion

RESEARCH METHODS

This quantitative research examines the effect of Professional skepticism and Professional Ethics on the Accuracy of Giving Auditor opinions. Primary data is the most important kind of data because it is the data that is collected first. The survey was conducted by distributing questionnaires to public accounting firms in Bandung. The number of respondents was as many as 56. This study looked at the population of public accounting firms in Bandung. The sampling technique used was to group things together and take a sample from each group. The clusters in this study are several auditors who work at the Public Accounting Firm in Bandung. They are all willing to be sampled. In this study, multiple regression analysis is used to test hypotheses. This is done with the help of the SPSS program. Multiple regression is a way to predict how a relationship between two different variables will change over time (George & Mallery, 2019; Suryanto, 2015).

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The Accuracy published of Auditor Opinion is highest for the Unqualified Opinion indicator, with a mean score of 4.01. This is included in the "Good" category. The Suspension indicator on Unqualified Opinion With Explanatory Language shows that 68% of the time, the opinion is qualified. The mean score is 3.14, which is in the "Good" category. The Professional Skepticism variable measures how much people in a given situation believe in skepticism. The maximum value is found in the Self Determination indicator, which measures how people feel about being able to make their own decisions. The mean score for this indicator is 4.11, which is included in the "Good" category. The Suspension on Judgment indicator shows that 68% of kids in this group have been suspended at least once. That means kids in this group are more likely to get into trouble than other kids. However, the mean score for this group is 3.14, which means that most kids in this group are still doing okay. The data in the professional ethics variable shows that 85.18% of the time, people have acted with integrity. This is shown by the high score on the integrity indicator and means that these people are usually honest and responsible. The minimum percentage value found in the indicators of the scope and nature of services is about 71%. This means that the services provided meet the minimum standards

required by the community. The mean score for the "Good" category is 3.57, which means that this type of service is good overall.

Table 2: Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.869	5.630		1.930	.059
	Professional Skepticism (X1)	.696	.209	.515	3.324	.002
	Professional Ethics (X2)	.466	.219	.329	2.127	.038

a. Dependent Variable: Accuracy publish of Auditor Opinion (Y)

The coefficient of determination shows how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In this case, Professional Skepticism (X1) and Professional Ethics (X2) both contribute 66.4% influence on the Accuracy Publish of Auditor Opinion (Y). In comparison (1-R²), 33.6% of the rest is the magnitude of the contribution of the result given by other variables not examined.

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. I Error I of the Estimate
1	.815 ^a	.664	.652	5.67660

a. Predictors: (Constant), Professional Ethics (X2), Professional Skepticism (X1)
b. Dependent Variable: Accuracy Publish Of Auditor Opinion (Y)

The impact of Professional skepticism (X1) and Professional Ethics (X2) on the accuracy of Accuracy Publish of Auditor Opinion (Y) is 66.4%. Based on the calculation results, it looks like the value of tcount is 3,324. This means that the signal has a certain strength or importance. $0.002 < 0.05$. The value of the count (3.324) is greater than the value of the table (2.006), which means that Ho is not a good choice. The 95% confidence level means that it is very likely that the Accuracy published of Auditor Opinion will be affected by Professional Skepticism.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Professional Skepticism on the Accuracy of Giving Auditor's Opinion

Based on the description of the analysis, the percentage of Questioning of Mind is at the level of 44.46% and a mean score of 4.01 is included in the "Good" category. Another indicator is Suspension of judgment, which based on the description of the analysis has a percentage of 63% and a mean score of 3, 14 are in the "Good" category. This shows that the auditor should not be hasty in making decisions. Prudence requires the auditor to carefully plan and supervise

every work that is his responsibility. Auditors must also always conduct a Search of Knowledge. Based on the description of the analysis it is at the level of 75% and the mean score is 3.75 in the "Good" category. These results indicate that auditors have a high desire to conduct a search related to the latest knowledge that must be understood and followed by developments. An Auditor must have Interpersonal Understanding. This indicator has a percentage of 78.21% and a mean score of 3.91 and is included in the "Good" category. It can be said that the auditor is more skeptical of the client's statement and seeks other relevant information. In addition, the auditor must have self-confidence, this indicator has a percentage of 77.32% and a mean score of 3.87 is included in the "Good" category. These results indicate that an auditor always has high professional confidence in acting on the collection of existing evidence. Another indicator is Self-determination, this indicator has a percentage of 82.14% and a mean score of 4.11 and is included in the "Good" category. These results indicate that the auditor has high self-determination. An auditor must always be objective and candid in making existing audit reports. According to the statistical results, it shows that the Professional Skepticism variable has a significant level of 0.02, which is less than 0.05. The t-value of 3,324 indicates a positive influence on the dependent variable or the Accuracy of Providing Audit Opinions. So it can be said that Professional Skepticism has a positive and significant effect on the Accuracy of Giving Audit Opinions.

As a professional, auditors are asked to be professionally skeptical by always questioning and critically assessing audit evidence. Be professional and skeptical in the audit process to consider and evaluate the competence of audit evidence that has been collected objectively. The auditor should not assume that management is being honest, but the possibility that they are being dishonest should still be considered. At the same time, the auditor should not assume that management is beyond doubt of its honesty. Skepticism is a manifestation of objectivity. Skepticism does not mean being cynical, overly critical, or insulting. The auditor's professional skepticism will lead him to inquire about any cues that indicate the possibility of fraud. Low professional skepticism dulls the auditor's sensitivity to fraud, both actual and potential, or to red flags that indicate errors and fraud. Auditors with their knowledge, experience, competence, and intuition must be able to detect audit risks that may occur. So that the audit procedures that are made will be able to increase the auditor's chances of detecting financial statements that contain material misstatements. If this is done with a strong commitment and responsibility to carry out audit work based on professional skepticism, it will have a positive effect on the resulting audit quality. The results of this study indicate that professional skepticism and professional ethics can affect the Accuracy Publish of Auditor Opinion. This study is in line with research conducted by (Nurjanah & Kartika, 2016) that ethics significantly affects the provision of audit opinions.

Effect of Professional Ethics on the Accuracy of Giving Auditor's Opinion

Based on the description analysis, the responsibility indicator has a percentage of 75.71% and a mean score of 3.78 which is included in the "Good" category. The "Good" category in this case means that in carrying out audit work it has fulfilled its responsibilities. Responsibilities are not only related to the audit reports produced but also to safeguarding confidential

information owned by clients. The auditor must respect the confidentiality of information obtained in the course of performing professional services and may not use or disclose such information without approval unless there are professional or legal rights and obligations to disclose it. Confidentiality is not merely a matter of disclosing information, confidentiality also requires the auditor to obtain information while performing professional services and not use or be involved in activities using that information for personal gain or the benefit of third parties.

Auditors are responsible not only to clients but also to society. The public interest indicator based on the results of the analysis has a percentage of 83.21% with a mean score of 4.16 which is included in the "Good" category. This shows that the auditor has understood that the public accounting profession has an obligation to act in a manner that prioritizes the public interest and respects public trust. Meanwhile, the integrity indicator based on the results of the analysis has a percentage of 85.18% with a mean score of 4.26 which is in the "Very Good" category. The "Very Good" category in this case means that in carrying out the audit work, the respondent has fulfilled integrity as a public accountant by being honest, forthright, and acting decisively within the scope of the audit work.

Objectivity and independence are attitudes that an auditor must have. Based on the results of the analysis description, objectivity and integrity indicators have a percentage of 82.50% and a mean score of 4.12 is included in the "Good" category. This means that the auditor has maintained objectivity and is free from conflicts of interest in carrying out his professional responsibilities. The principle of objectivity based on the Indonesian Institute of Accountants (IAI) requires that the auditor be fair, impartial, intellectually honest, not prejudiced or biased, and free from conflicts of interest or being under the influence of other parties. Another indicator of professionalism is thoroughness. Based on the results of the analysis description, the accuracy indicator has a percentage of 77.32% and a mean score of 3.86 is included in the "Good" category. This shows that the auditor pays attention to professional technical and ethical standards, continues to strive to improve the competence and quality of the services he provides, and carries out professional responsibilities according to his best abilities. An auditor must be aware of the competence he has and not describe himself as having reliability in carrying out audit work that he does not actually have. This relates to the scope and nature of the services provided. Based on the results of the description of the analysis, the scope and nature of services indicators have a percentage of 71.43% and a mean score of 3.57 in the "Good" category. It can be interpreted that the auditor understands the scope and nature of the services that should be provided in accordance with the principles of the professional code of conduct. The auditor should pay attention to the audit assignment given whether it exceeds the competency possessed or beyond the auditor's understanding. Based on the indicators mentioned above, forming the auditor's professional ethics variable, an average value of 3.96 is included in the "Good" category because this value is in the interval between 3.41-4.20. It can be concluded that the understanding and application of the auditor's professional ethics in conducting audit examinations at KAPs in the City of Bandung that is registered with the Financial Services Authority 2022 meet the requirements to be said to be good.

Based on the statistical results, shows that the Professional Ethics variable has a significant level of 0.38, which is greater than 0.05. The t-value of 2,127 indicates that the influence is positive on the dependent variable or the Accuracy of Providing Audit Opinions. So it can be said that Professional Ethics has a positive and significant effect on the Accuracy of Giving Audit Opinions. This research is in line with research conducted by Nurjanah & Kartika (2016) that ethics has a significant effect on giving audit opinions. The results are the same as the research by Widiarini & Suputra (2017) that professional ethics has a positive effect on the accuracy of giving audit opinions to KAPs in Bali. Meanwhile, Anwar's research Anwar (2018) is not in line with this research because professional ethics has an effect but is not significant in giving audit opinions. In addition, the results of research by K. C. Dewi, Wijayanti, & Suhendro (2017) stated that ethics has no significant effect on audit opinion.

Professional ethics has a positive and significant effect on the accuracy of giving audit opinions, supported by the case of Indonesia Corruption Watch (ICW) which asked nine public accounting firms to be investigated in Jakarta based on reports from the Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPKP) which were suspected of collusion with banks. Audited. Nine out of ten KAPs that conducted audits of around 36 troubled banks did not conduct audits according to audit standards. The results of these audits were not in accordance with the facts, resulting in the majority of the banks being audited including the banks whose business activities were suspended by the government. The nine KAPs have violated the professional ethics of an auditor. From this, there were several violations of professional ethics committed by the auditor including the auditor not reflecting professional competence and prudence, the auditor did not understand the criteria for the principle of income so he could not detect that there was an error in writing the financial statements not in accordance with applicable standards. In addition, a professional accountant must comply with relevant laws and regulations and should avoid actions that could discredit the profession. Based on the case above, shows that the audit activities carried out have not been maximal, both professional ethics and professional skepticism in the company. In maintaining the level of public trust and the accuracy of giving opinions, public accountants must always carry out audit programs in a professional manner, committed to auditing standards and ethics in providing audit services to their clients.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on data analysis and discussion of the conclusions regarding the influence of professional skepticism and professional ethics on the accuracy of providing audit opinions to KAPs registered with the Financial Services Authority in the city of Bandung in 2022, it is possible to conclude as follows:

- 1) Professional skepticism affects the Accuracy of published Auditor Opinion, so it can be concluded that in formulating an opinion, every auditor must have an attitude of professional skepticism.

- 2) Professional ethics has a positive and significant effect on the accuracy of providing audit opinions at public accounting firms in Bandung, which are registered with the Financial Services Authority. The higher the application of professional ethics by the auditor, the higher the accuracy of the audit opinion given.

Suggestion

Based on the research that has been done, suggestions that can be considered include:

- 1) Based on respondents' answers to the professional skepticism variable, the Suspension on Judgment indicator is still quite low compared to the other five indicators that make up the auditor professionalism variable. In this case, there is nothing wrong with the auditor further improving experience and intuition can also assist the auditor in making decisions to produce better reports.
- 2) When viewed from the recapitulation of respondents' answers to the variable of professional ethics, the indicators of the scope and nature of services have the lowest values compared to the other five needles. This value can be better if the auditor can pay more attention to the audit assignment given, whether it exceeds the competence possessed or is beyond the auditor's understanding.”

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